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ECONOMY

Theoretical and methodological basis of the organization of state financial control

Hakimov Nodir Nazarovich

Researcher Tashkent State Economic of University,
Tashkent, UZBEKISTAN

Email id: saidnazarov86@gmail.com

Abstract: The article examines aspects of the organization of state financial control and studies its theoretical and methodological foundations. The state of state financial control is also analyzed. Based on the results of the analysis, a scientific proposal and practical recommendations aimed at the organization of state financial control were developed.

Key words: financial control, monetary funds, financial resources, budget, market, price.

Financial control is actually related to the financial category, and when redistributing part of the national income created within the national economy through the financial category, there is a need for state monitoring as a form of determining how the national income distributed as a financial resource is used by its recipients. implements through its organizations, determines the functions and tasks of these organizations, puts financial issues before them, monitors whether the financial resources spent through state monetary funds are spent on purpose and in their place. And this in itself creates a comprehensive relationship with the state financial control as the basis of the control function of finance. In fact, in the study of financial control and its specific aspects, it requires a theoretical analysis of the scientific-theoretical studies conducted in this regard.

In particular, S., who conducted deep scientific research in this regard. Platonova defines the category of financial control as follows, that is, "the concept of financial control is the authorized activity of the implementation of continuous, preventive, current and subsequent financial control in order to effectively manage the actions of the financial resources of the state and local authorities at all levels related to public finance." In turn, S. Platonova proved the effectiveness of the

principle of "prevention of harm" in the implementation of state financial control. In the opinion of the author, it is necessary to pay a lot of attention to the preventive approach in the organization and implementation of the state financial control, so that the costs of financial control will bear fruit.

T.Pereverzeva in her scientific research on this subject "state financial control is an effective means of increasing the efficiency of the use of budget expenditures and creating a basis for building a democratic, socially oriented state and increasing the well-being of the entire population. multi-functional activity carried out by internal and external state control subjects aimed at assessment.

Russian economist A.Migachev studied the mutual characteristics of the organization of state financial control and its implementation between Russia and France. In his research, A. Migichev showed the general characteristics of state financial control, and defined it as the financial sphere of the state as the object of financial control, the authorized bodies conducting financial control as the subject, and the state and movement of financial resources, the forms and methods of transfer, as the sphere of financial control. shows that A. Migichev dwells on the principles of the organization of state financial control and points out such principles as independence, competence of state financial control bodies, legality, openness of implementation, efficiency, systematicity and flexibility.

According to A. Migichev, state financial control is a complex, multifaceted phenomenon with deep historical roots, which includes the activities of state bodies to check the legal and effective use of funds in the state sector, to identify and prevent financial and economic risks, and to prevent violations of financial discipline by recipients of funds. defines it as an economic process that enables the identification and prosecution of guilty persons.

State mechanisms of financial control, in turn, centralized monetary funds and processes related to them, as well as implementation of financial transactions in the national economy and international financial relations based on the requirements of the law, are understood by the competent authorities of the state in various ways and means.

Financial control, in fact, as an integral part of the state or other economic entities that exercise financial control, has its roots in distribution relations. As a matter of fact, it is a very important issue to ensure the effective use of limited financial resources in the implementation of the optimal distribution of the national income, which is the main financial function of the state, to those who participated directly and indirectly in its creation. It should be noted that the root of financial control goes back to distribution relations, but the main factor that requires it in an economic objective way is the need and obligations to obtain maximum profit in the conditions of limited resources or to operate in a uniform manner, and to use the funds given from above.

In our opinion, state financial control is the process of controlling the formation, distribution, use of funds, the state and movement of financial relations and the correct implementation of operations by the authorized bodies of the state, the public and economic entities using financial methods and tools. understood. In general, state financial control covers financial (economic), social, management and legal relations. If we explain more broadly, since the state financial control is primarily related to financial relations, it expresses the harmony of its redistributive and control functions as an important element of the financial category and always regulates monetary relations. On the other hand, when the state financial control is taken into account, social relations are embodied in it, and by carrying out state financial control, it encourages the enterprises that are the objects of control and the financially responsible persons there not to violate the laws, to be honest, not to embezzle other people's funds, and to have mutual respect for the material and technical base and wealth of the enterprise. and compels when necessary, and these essentially characterize its social characteristics.

In the process of financial management, the process of financial control is mainly carried out through two different mechanisms, that is, through state mechanisms and market mechanisms. Market mechanisms of financial control are mainly market demand and supply, consumption process, price factors, distribution of resources, inflation and similar market instruments, the financial activity of

economic entities takes place in a certain direction, and the financial levers reflecting market rules control the financial activity of enterprises and households. ranks, and this ranking has the character of financial control.

In our opinion, state financial control is the process of controlling the formation, distribution, use of funds, the state and movement of financial relations and the correct implementation of operations by the authorized bodies of the state, the public and economic entities using financial methods and tools. understood.

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HISTORY

At the end of the 19th century and at the beginning of the 20th century, the administrative-territorial division of Turkestan and the adoption of management regulations.

Bakhtiyor Sabirjonovich Boltabaev

Namangan state university Teacher

Abstract: In this article, after the colonization of Central Asia by the Russian Empire, the development of regulations, projects, laws for managing the territory of the country, the division of the territory of Turkestan into administrative territorial units, depicting local protests.

Key words: The division of the territory of Turkestan into administrative-territorial units, the temporary management charter, the introduction of management charters, management projects, and the increase of protests among the local population against management procedures are described.

In 1865-1867, the territories occupied by the Russian Empire in Central Asia were included in the Turkestan region under the Orenburg Governorate. In April 1867, the Emperor of the Russian Empire, Alexander II, approved the project of the Special Committee on the establishment of the General Governorate of Turkestan - the land of Turkestan. On July 23, an imperial decree was issued on the establishment of the Turkestan General Governorship. The creation of a new political-administrative unit of the empire meant the end of the initial stage of the conquest of the territory of Central Asia. This, in turn, required the territorial expansion of the empire and the economic development of new territories. In addition, the new administrative unit was supposed to play the role of a springboard for Russia's wider penetration into the region. For this, first of all, it was necessary to solve the issue of administrative structure and management of the country.

Therefore, on July 11, 1867, "The Draft Regulation on the Management of the Yettisuv and Syrdarya Regions" was introduced. The "military situation" factor was of decisive importance in the development of the first program documents for the management of the Turkestan General Governorship. They appeared with the

conquest of new territories and had a “temporary” nature as a rule. For example, in 1867, the “Regulation on Management in the Syrdarya and Yettisuv Regions” was introduced “for three years as an experiment”. In addition, in June 1868 - Provisional regulations for the management of Zarafshan district", - Provisional regulations for the management of Fergana region of 1873” [1. Abdurakhimova N.A., Ergashev F.R. Tsarist colonial system in Turkestan. - T.: Akademiya, 2002. -34 p.] -The regulation of May 21, 1874 on the management of the Amu Darya department" was also developed and adopted. But all of them were in force until the adoption of the 1886 Regulation.

The existence of various temporary regulations and the absence of a single normative document led to certain difficulties in management. Measures to eliminate this situation are implemented by the metropolis through various activities, in particular, inspections. In 1882, F.K.Girs, who conducted inspection work in the country, in his report: - Due to the fact that the military-people's administration has outlived its usefulness and is unable to meet the current needs of the country, general-based administration based on local conditions it should be introduced,” he says. According to the results of F.K.Girs' inspection work, by 1886, the study and reform of the country's administrative structure began. As a result, the Regulation “On the Administration of the Turkestan Territory” was adopted. [2. Tukhtametov F.T. Pravovoe polozhenie Turkestana v Rossiyskoy imperii (second half of XIX century). Monograph. Ufa, BashGU, 1999.-67 p]

The Regulation of 1886 formalized the relations between the institutions of various ministries and the Governor General of Turkestan, which had not been legally regulated for a long time. Judiciary, finance, control, educational and post-telegraph institutions will be placed under the governor-general of Turkestan. In the provinces, their units directly subordinated to the ministries and departments in the country appeared. The territory of Turkestan was governed on the basis of this Charter until the collapse of the Russian Empire in 1917.

In 1867 - 1886, the Turkestan General Governorate was divided into regions and uezds in order to further facilitate the management of the country. In places

bordering Central Asian khanates, instead of uezds, corresponding military-territorial units - districts, departments and regions were established.

Initially, the General Governorate of Turkestan was divided into two regions: Syrdaryo with its center in Tashkent and Ettisuv region with its center in Verniy. Later, the following administrative-territorial units were additionally established at the expense of the occupied territories: in 1868 Zarafshan district, the center of which was in Samarkand; In 1874, the Amudarya department with its center in Petroaleksandrovsk (Tortkol); In 1876, due to the dissolution of the Kokan Khanate, Fergana region, whose center is in the city of New Margilan (Fergana). Yettisuv region was divided into five districts - Sergiopolsk, Kopal, Verniy, Issykkol and Tokmok. In 1882, he was removed from the Turkestan Governor General. A total of seven uezds - Avliyo-ota, Kazala, Kurama (the center is Koylyk village), Perovsk, Turkestan, Khojand and Shymkent uezds were established within Syrdarya region. The city of Tashkent established an independent administrative unit. Amudarya branch was also part of Syrdarya. [3. Tukhtametov F.T. Pravovoe polozhenie Turkestana v Rossiyskoy imperii (second half of XIX century). Monograph. Ufa, BashGU, 1999.-67 p]

The territory of Zarafshan district was initially divided into Samarkand and Kattakorgan departments. In 1871, a new administrative-territorial unit - mountain districts - was added to them. It was built from small hills above the Zarafshan river. The Samarkand department consisted of three districts, and the Kattakorgan department consisted of one district. In 1873, the Amudarya department, which was established in a part of the territory separated from Khiva Khanate, was divided into Chimboy and Shurakhan sections.

There is a total of seven uezds in the territory of Fergana region - Andijan, Ko'kan, Margilon, Namangan, Osh and Chust, and at the same time Chimyon (since 1879 - Isfara) uezd was formed, its territory was 1881 - was distributed to Ko'kan and Marglan uezds. The head of this system was appointed by the tsar and considered the governor-general subordinate to the Ministry of Defense of Russia. He was both the head of the civil administration and the commander of the troops of the

Turkestan military district. According to the laws of the whole empire, the governor-general was made "the chief guardian of autocratic territories, the inviolability of state interests, and the strict execution of laws."

Speaking about the specific features of the administration of the regions of the Turkestan General Governorate, it should first be noted that the administration system in the country is highly militarized. Provinces included in the General Governorate were initially governed on the basis of temporary Regulations developed separately for each of them. In 1867, "Regulations on management in the Syrdarya and Yetisuv regions", in 1868 "Temporary rules for the management of Zarafshan district", in 1873 "Temporary regulations for the management of Fergana region", in 1874 "Amu Darya Bodimin" regulation on management" was developed and adopted was done. All of them, in essence, confirmed "the unity of military and administrative power and its unification in one line" [4. Ziyaeva D. Cities of Uzbekistan in the second half of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century. - T., 2014;] The chairman of the regional administration was the assistant military governor. Regional administrations performed administrative, judicial, police, financial and economic functions.

According to the structure of regional administrations, they were made up of divisions, and their number increased with the establishment and strengthening of the colonial system. For example, if in 1867 only three departments - distribution, economic and judicial departments - operated in the administrations of Syrdarya and Yettisuv regions, then by the mid-1980s, intermediate border, construction, agricultural medicine, veterinary and accounting departments were opened. In addition, a printing press and statistics committees were established under each regional administration. The military governor was engaged in the division of responsibilities between regional administration units. In order to solve scientific, technical, medical and other issues considered important for this or that region, contingency councils were established under regional administrations. Experts were invited to act as consultants and experts in these councils.

The duties of the employees of the distribution department included the following:

selection, sorting and publication of territorial division and construction of the province, decrees, orders, orders of the governor-general, military governors and government; issuing legislation and informational documents; it is necessary to deal with service and vacation work of regional officials.

In solving the mentioned issues, the officials did not follow the principles of administrative activity, legality and legal protection. Their personal desire often prevailed over any instructions and laws. In general, any public structure in the country could not function without the management, supervision or control of specially organized bodies and officials working in them according to the laws of 1867. The colonial power's "intrusion" into the spheres of life of the indigenous population and its attempt to regulate it are more clearly visible in the structure and functions of the lower authorities. Bolis (volost) was considered the lowest link in the territorial organization system. However, bolis management was consistently introduced only in Fergana region and Zarafshan district. In other places, due to the large number of nomadic populations, along with bolis, elderships were also established in densely populated regions. Khojand uyezd has its own characteristics, its territory was divided into three regions - Khojand, Oratepa and Jizzakh.

In general, the natural, historical, economic and national features of the country were not taken into account in the administrative-territorial division of Turkestan by Russian.

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MEDICINE

Application of the hemoben hemostatic implant in the model of spleen damage in the background of hypocoagulation

**Sadykov R.A., Khodzhiev D.Sh., Sultanov S.A.,
Kadyrov M.Zh., Sharifjonov S.M.**

Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Surgery named after academician V. Vakhidov, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Relevance: In surgery, various hemostatic sponges are often used to stop internal bleeding. In conditions of hypocoagulation, stopping bleeding and its control subsequently becomes an even more difficult task that needs to be solved, since most topical drugs are ineffective in conditions of hypocoagulation. The parenchyma of the spleen does not shrink during trauma, so bleeding can be intense and prolonged.

Materials and methods: To assess the possibility of stopping bleeding from the wound of the spleen under conditions of drug hypocoagulation, experiments were performed on mature white male rats weighing 220-280 g. Animals were kept in 4 individuals in one cage and were kept in a vivarium and a balanced diet. In the experimental group of rats (10), an aspirin tablet 1 g per 100 ml of water was added to the water. An approximate calculation was 10 mg per 200 g of animal weight per day. 7 days after the start of taking the drug, the Lee-White blood clotting time was checked by taking blood from the tail vein. Under the condition of VSC elongation by 50-70%, experimental studies were started.

The formed wound of the spleen, according to the method developed by us, caused active mixed bleeding, which, without the use of hemostatic measures, led to death in 80% of cases from ongoing blood loss. To stop bleeding against the background of hypocoagulation, we used domestic local hemostatic preparations: a haemo sponge obtained from animal collagen; hemostatic domestic implant in the form of Hemoben powder.

Studies on 5 outbred white rats with an average weight of 220 ± 5 g were carried out using domestically produced hemo sponges. When modeling damage to the spleen under general anesthesia, active bleeding from the spleen was stopped by

applying fragments of hemosponges corresponding to the size of the damage to the spleen. Usually, 0.7x2 cm in size. During the operation, the sponge quickly became saturated with blood and subsequently lost its properties. In this connection, to completely stop the bleeding, it took 3 times the use of hemospong fragments. As complete primary hemostasis was achieved, blood loss amounted to 2 ml. During a 10-minute observation, a gradual saturation of the sponge with incoming blood was noted.

Results: Postoperative mortality within a day after surgery was 2 out of 5 individuals. The cause of death was continued bleeding from the wound of the spleen. In the rest of the animals that were withdrawn from the experiment on the next day, it was revealed that the spleen is in a massive adhesive infiltrate in the form of loose adhesions. There are traces of blood in the lateral parts of the abdomen. There are hematomas of varying severity in the area of the applied hemosponges. Under conditions of hypocoagulation, damage to the spleen causes profuse blood loss with a fatal outcome. The use of domestically produced hemosponges is ineffective in stopping bleeding from a spleen wound. There was a high risk of recurrent bleeding in the postoperative period. Thus, the use of a hemostatic sponge in an isolated form for hypocoagulable bleeding cannot be recommended in clinical practice.

Research in the experimental group was carried out on 5 white male rats with an average weight of 230+6g. The experimental conditions are the same as in the group with hemosponge. Upper median laparotomy under general anesthesia. The spleen was removed into the wound and damage was modeled with the development of mixed active bleeding. The use of Hemoben powder under conditions of hypocoagulable bleeding led to rapid impregnation of the powder with blood with the formation of a gel. Subsequent blood flows required repeated application of Hemoben powder. A complete stop of bleeding was achieved after 3-4 repeated applications of Hemoben powder with the formation of a rather loose thrombus. When observed for 10 minutes, there was a gradual saturation and blood soaking of the superficially located dry powder Hemoben. Subsequently, a thrombus of sufficiently large size, not dense enough, was formed. However, hemostasis was

achieved in all cases. Blood loss amounted to approximately 1-2 ml. There were no deaths in the postoperative period. When withdrawing from the experiment 1 day after the operation, a rather massive thrombus was detected in the area of the spleen wound with involvement of the omentum, surrounded by loose adhesions. There were traces of blood in the lateral sections of the abdomen.

The studies have established that in conditions of hypocoagulable bleeding from a simulated spleen wound, the use of the hemostatic drug Hemoben has a noticeable hemostasis with the formation of a loose thrombus on the surface of the wound. However, the consumption of the drug increases by 2-3 times, and the thrombus tends to grow in the postoperative period. Thus, despite the sufficient effectiveness of Hemoben hemostatic in spleen injuries against the background of hypocoagulation, isolated use of the drug may be insufficient in clinical observations. Analysis of coagulogram parameters and peripheral blood before and after surgery after implantation of hemostatic material did not reveal significant changes from the norm.

Conclusion: The study of the effect of the Hemoben hemostatic film on the biochemical parameters of blood serum before and after the operation did not reveal significant changes. The data obtained allowed us to conclude that "Hemoben" does not have a negative effect on the biochemical parameters of the blood.

The conducted experimental studies have shown that the developed new hemostatic material in the form of a powder can be used to stop parenchymal bleeding. Under conditions of medical hypocoagulation, Hemoben provides good and stable hemostasis, which significantly exceeds the parameters of a hemostatic sponge. In case of damage to the spleen against the background of hypocoagulation, Hemospong is ineffective, while Hemoben allows achieving hemostasis, however, the recurrence rate can increase up to 20%, depending on the degree of damage to the spleen capsule.

Dependence of the state of teeth and oral hygiene in children with a changeable bite.

Abdirimova G.I., Nazirova S.H., Safarova Sh.U.

Annotation. Studies of many domestic and foreign authors have established a direct connection between the hygienic state of the oral cavity and the frequency and intensity of dental caries. It has been established that in absolutely the majority of children whose teeth are poorly cared for, the carious process proceeds 30-40% more actively (S.S. Gulomov. 2018). The relevance of hygienic education and upbringing of children and their parents is explained by the insufficient degree of awareness in the issues of dental prevention. In addition, it has been reliably established that the low sanitary and cultural level of parents coincides with the unsatisfactory condition of teeth in children.

Keywords. Hygiene, dentistry, prevention, enamel demineralization, caries.

With a mild degree of demineralization, a satisfactory hygienic condition of the oral cavity was more often determined. With an average degree of lesion, the hygienic condition of the oral cavity was more often unsatisfactory. With a high degree of demineralization, as a rule, there was an unsatisfactory and poor hygienic condition of the oral cavity. Consequently, with the deterioration of the hygienic condition of the oral cavity in children, there is an increase in the demineralization of tooth enamel. The occurrence and development of the carious process largely depends on the abundance of plaque. However, there is an opinion that the qualitative characteristic of plaque has much more. When examining the selected children, we paid attention to the presence of plaque, its localization, layer thickness, pigmentation, and determined its cariesogenic activity. Thus, an in-depth study of the prevalence of dental caries and oral hygiene in primary school children allowed us to make the following conclusions, the study of the prevalence and intensity of dental caries among the examined in the study group were: at the age of 7 years $69.2 \pm 2.87\%$, at the age of 8 years $72.5 \pm 2.21\%$, at the age of 9 years $74.6 \pm 2.3\%$, at the age of 10 years $80.1 \pm 1.2\%$, in the control group they were respectively: in the first group $68.7 \pm 2.8\%$, in the second group $73.1 \pm 2.1\%$, in the third group $76.1 \pm$

1.8%, in the fourth group $81.7 \pm 1.7\%$. Children with intact caries were 25.6%. The average intensity of caries in children aged 7-10 years in the city of Tashkent ranged from 2.87 ± 0.21 to 4.02 ± 0.31 . Everywhere there is a slight excess of the prevalence of caries and its intensity in boys than in girls.

PEDAGOGY

Negative and positive concepts within the lexeme "family"

Ishkobilova Khulkar

Teacher, Uzbekistan State World Languages University
hulkarishqobilova@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

From the point of view of semantics, the concept of family includes both negative and positive concepts. These concepts have a certain importance in human life and are an important factor that decorates their life and distinguishes them from others as conscious beings. The positive concepts that manifest the above spirituality are valued by humanity and are considered national values.

Keywords: concept, concept of family, human life, negative and positive concepts.

Negative concepts about the family are: betrayal, divorce, war-quarrels, childlessness, discord, illness, distrust, unkindness.

Positive concepts, in turn: attitude, value, cultural and spiritual factors

1. Thought
2. Solidarity
3. Respect
4. Virtue
5. Respect
6. Kindness
7. Hospitality
8. Attention
9. Kindness
- 10.

Loyalty is divided into others. In fact, the first things that people value are these values.

This concept has been defined by researchers from all sides. N.Sh. Almatov says that values are a set of cultural and spiritual factors. The concepts defining the positive characteristics of the above family are, in turn, national values of spiritual and moral content. These terms have been ingrained in the blood of our people for

centuries, and they have matured and developed on the basis of these concepts. Proof of these views can be seen in every stratum of the people. Each of these words is defined with separate examples. Below we will consider the composition of the term andisha.

"Andisha- [thought, thinking] 1. A consideration that is carried out thinking about the next, the consequences or keeping in mind. Andisha's horse is timid. Proverb" [Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language, 2006, p.84]. As we can see, the word is proved by a proverb in the dictionary. That is, it is said that it is not necessary to make cowards of people who think about the consequences of their actions. It is important for a person to live in harmony with his fellow citizens, family members, peers, elders, and everyone living in the society. In addition, the word "andisha" is associated with the word's "shame", "shame" and "chastity" and has these meanings in mind. We can see the works written by the great representatives of Uzbek literature as a clear proof of this quality. If you look at the work of Abdulla Qadiri, the founder of Uzbek novel writing, he is a poet who wrote his work under the slogan of "what will we leave for posterity". He emphasizes that every nation has its own history, so it has unique spiritual and national values.

First of all, the independence of Uzbekistan pays great attention to raising the morale of our people and restoring our values. In this regard, it is clear that the works of our poets and writers, who lived and created in different eras, serve for the perfect formation of the ideas of independence and national independence ideology. In particular, we can witness how glorified our national values are in the novel "Gone Days", which is considered a masterpiece of Uzbek fiction. The actions of one of the main characters of the play, Kumush's attitude toward Uzbek girls, shying away from Otabek when they see him, shyly talking behind the curtain without being able to look directly at his parents, and pretending to express that Otabek is in love with him are like sinners, unable to look at Hassanali's face. their shame is a clear proof of our word.

These centuries-old values are being refined and are being propagated day by day even in our current age.

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The role of independent study in foreign language teaching

Sh R. Akramov,

Associate Professor of the Faculty of Foreign Languages of TSPU named after Nizomi, Department of the Practical English Course

sakramov@mail.ru

Abstract: The article deals with the issues based on analyzing the importance of independent study in teaching foreign languages. We analyzed the notion of independent study and its role in education.

Keywords: foreign languages, science, independent study, educational process.

In recent years, there has been a marked increase in interest in independent work in organizing the educational process at all levels of education. This interest is not accidental. In modern conditions of the development of science, the rapid accumulation and updating of information, it is impossible to educate a person for life, but it is important to instill in him an interest in the accumulation of knowledge, to teach him to learn. Therefore, the desire to develop in students the ability to independently acquire knowledge and quickly adapt to new areas of activity comes to the fore. The student must not only acquire a certain amount of knowledge, but also be able to independently draw conclusions, think creatively, be able to independently replenish their knowledge, and navigate the rapidly growing flow of information.

The organization of independent work, its management is a responsible and complex work of every teacher. The education of activity and independence must be considered as an integral part of the education of students. This task appears before every teacher among the tasks of paramount importance.

Independent work is not an end in itself. It is a means of fighting for deep and solid knowledge of students, a means of forming their activity and independence as personality traits, and developing their mental abilities. And, perhaps, the main function of independent work is the formation of a highly cultured personality. Man develops only in independent intellectual and spiritual activity.

Success largely depends on the organization of independent work, which contributes to increasing the effectiveness of training, is of great educational importance. Independent work brings up the cognitive activity of students, is an important condition for self-organization and self-discipline in mastering the methods of cognitive activity, develops in students a psychological attitude towards independent systematic replenishment of their knowledge and the development of skills to navigate in the flow of various information when solving cognitive problems.

The desire to acquire knowledge independently and creatively, to complete tasks that require the manifestation of a critical mind, imagination, fantasy, dreams - these are indispensable conditions for the emergence of a deep interest in academic subjects. Independent work is considered as a specific form of a student's learning activity, characterized by all its features. This is a form of self-education associated with the learning activities of the student. The concept of independent work of a student in modern didactics necessarily correlates with the organizing role of the teacher.

Independent work is understood as a variety of types of individual and collective activities of students carried out by them in class and extracurricular activities or at home on assignments without the direct participation of the teacher. The general pedagogical definition of extra-curricular and out-of-school work, according to which it represents various types of educational and educational activities of students organized and conducted by the school during extracurricular time, is the basis for considering the independent activities of students.

Currently, there are several approaches to the disclosure of the essence of the concept of independent work. According to various researchers, independent work searched as a form of education (N.G. Dairy, I.I. Ilyasov, etc.); teaching method (A.V. Usova); type of learning activity (R.B. Sroda, O.A. Nilson); a means of organizing and managing cognitive activity (P.I. Pidkasisty, E.L. Belkin).

Most actively used in didactics is the definition given by B.P. Esipov - independent work of students included in the learning process - this is such work

that is performed without the direct participation of the teacher, on his instructions, at a time specially presented for this, while students consciously strive to achieve the goal set in the task, showing their efforts and expressing in in one way or another, the results of their mental or physical (or both) actions.

As the main features of independent work, B.P. Esipov identifies:

- activities of students without assistance;
- availability of a task;
- lack of direct intervention of the teacher;
- specially allotted time for the task;
- registration of results in one form or another.

P.I.Pidkasty, investigating this problem, notes that the definition of independent work should reflect the creativity of the student and the unity of the procedural and logical-content aspects of independent activity. Each of these levels, although they are allocated conditionally, objectively exists. Giving an independent task to a student at a higher level is, at best, wasting time in the lesson in vain.

Naturally, the maximum program for any creative teacher is to bring as many children as possible to the fourth level of independence. However, it should be remembered that the path to it lies only through the three previous levels. Accordingly, the program of actions of the teacher is built when organizing independent work in the classroom.

It follows that it is possible to improve not only the quality of organizing and conducting independent work of students in English lessons, but also to facilitate its implementation for the students themselves by observing simple requirements for it.

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Informatics as an essential component of lyceum education

Umurzokov Zokir, researcher,
SamSU academic lyceum, Uzbekistan

Abstract: It is well known that effective learning is directly dependent on the level of activity of students in this process. Currently, didactic psychologists are trying to find the most effective teaching methods to enhance and develop students' cognitive interest in the content of education. In this regard, many questions are related to the use of didactic games in the classroom. In this article, an attempt is made to consider and study the activation of the cognitive activity of lyceum students through the use of didactic games, which acts as a condition for the success of education.

Keywords and phrases: textbooks, workbooks, game techniques, entertaining questions, tasks, physical exercises, counting rhymes, poems, conversations, logical tasks

Today, informatics is regarded as an essential component of general education, which plays a significant role in solving the priority tasks of education - in the formation of a holistic worldview, a system-information picture of the world, educational and communication skills, and the basic mental qualities of a student's personality.

The widespread introduction of computer technologies in the educational process underlies almost all concepts of reforming the general education. Studies of domestic and foreign scientists have shown that computer science is a system-forming subject, such as mathematics or language, and together with them forms the basis of modern education.

The informatics course in the lyceum solves problems of a developing, ideological, technological nature and, in comparison with other lyceum disciplines, has a number of specific features due to the content of the material being studied. Mastering such concepts as "information" and "information processes" requires a certain life experience, various knowledge about the world around, the ability to think abstractly and draw logical conclusions.

The informatics course for students is characterized by a specific instrumental base, in which, in addition to the traditional elements of the lesson for this age group (textbooks, workbooks, game techniques at various stages of the lesson, there are entertaining questions, tasks, physical exercises, counting rhymes, poems, conversations, logical tasks etc.) includes a personal computer with the obligatory use of a keyboard and a mouse, as well as various computer game programs: teaching, developing, controlling.

For the harmonious interweaving of any lyceum subject, the development of which begins later than others, in the line of already studied educational disciplines, satellite subjects become important, which precede the study of the basic academic discipline or go in parallel with it, simultaneously performing an auxiliary function - contributing to the acquisition of the necessary skills and abilities. for more intensive development of the main subject.

In informatics lessons, optimal conditions are created to enhance the process of self-education of students through the use of computer technology. But this is almost impossible without the ability to fluent conscious reading.

Therefore, preparation for the introduction of a new subject "Informatics" can actually be carried out at every lesson, and a supporting role in its study can be played by all the disciplines studied in parallel, taking into account the adjustment of curricula aimed at introducing a new subject area "Informatics" into the curriculum.

As already mentioned, one of the tasks of the I propaedeutic course of informatics is the formation of students' ideas about information, its properties and information processes.

From the first days of the study, students work with different types of information in textbooks, books for extracurricular reading, notebooks, albums, audio and video recordings, learn to obtain the necessary knowledge from various sources, analyze, draw conclusions.

The tasks of the lyceum informatics course include mastering the skills of computer management and related information technologies by students, which, in turn, contributes to the improvement of subject methods.

Rich multimedia computer facilities, simplification of access to information resources lead to the emergence of new progressive pedagogical technologies, the activation of educational and cognitive activity of students (the creation of conditions that ensure the intensity of the formation and satisfaction of the cognitive needs of students), the intensification of learning, and open up wide opportunities for self-education.

Students can be introduced to new information technologies from the beginning by using the demonstration capabilities of a computer (electronic PowerPoint presentations, visiting educational sites) in lessons in various academic disciplines when explaining, consolidating and repeating the material.

To do this, it is enough to have one set in the classroom, which includes a computer, a projector, a demonstration screen, and also provide access to the Internet.

Classes using computer technologies not only enliven the learning process (which is especially important given the psychological characteristics of students, in particular, the long-term predominance of visual-figurative thinking over abstract-logical), but also increase learning motivation, arouse interest in the computer, desire learn to manage it.

Thus, we can conclude that the elements of the future subject "Informatics" are present in every lesson of students. It is only important to emphasize the information component of the subject area lessons in the context of objective information processes.

Work experience shows that lessons with computer support are characterized by high activity of all students, interest in the results of their activities, and a large volume of tasks completed.

The main result of the first year of teaching informatics is the creation of prerequisites for the formation of an educational and information environment in the

lessons of informatics in the following classes, under the influence of which the educational and cognitive activity of students is activated. In this case, the most important role function of the teacher becomes the identification of the cognitive needs and capabilities of each student, the creation of adequate conditions for his self-development in the process of creative activity.

Such a function is implemented with a consistent transition from the dominant position of the teacher to the role of an active consultant and coordinator of the educational process in partnerships between all its participants.

As a result, the student realizes the significance of his activity, which ultimately gives an increase in his motivation.

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STATE AND LAW

Legal nature of women's social rights

Dildora Anvarovna Anvarova,

Lecturer Department of Constitutional law
Tashkent State University of Law, Uzbekistan

email: hsti.anvarova@gmail.com

Abstract: The article analyzes the legal nature of women's social rights within the framework of constitutional law. The concept of women's social rights is given an author's definition. The scientific views of scientists regarding the social rights of people are analyzed.

Key words: women's rights, social rights, right to work, right to rest, freedom to choose a profession, right to use medical services, right to social security, equal rights, maternity protection, social discrimination, decree, legal guarantee, equality.

If the population of the world is about 7 billion, almost half of them are women, and they are the main participants in social relations. It is the concept of "women" that defines the essence of their rights and is evaluated as a social phenomenon that requires a special scientific approach. However, while analyzing the nature of women's rights, it is important to study their importance as a component of human rights and freedoms and the direct impact of the concept of "women" on the definition and implementation of rights and freedoms. Because the de facto (practical) application of rights is vitally important in terms of protecting women's rights and interests [4].

The issue of women is one of the issues that the world community always calls for intense discussion and urges to take legal measures. In particular, the United Nations requested the countries of the world to pay special attention to the rights and freedoms of women, who are the most needy and poor part of society during the quarantine period of the Covid-19 pandemic. However, women suffer from stereotypes in society, gender inequality and violence, discrimination, poverty, and cruel treatment. Many of them are not only subjected to violence in their own country due to their economic incapacity, but those who go to work in other countries as labor migrants are subjected to violence in different communities and

workplaces and are exploited as victims of human trafficking.

The above problems indicate the need to analyze scientific research related to the understanding of the essence and legal nature of women's social rights. When we study the scientific works of researchers who studied the essence of social rights, we see that they have different approaches to the essence of these rights. In particular, according to A.E. Kozlov, "Social rights are aimed at satisfying the important and vital needs of a person, regardless of the amount and quality of work performed by a person"[1].

N.W. Putilo: "Social rights are the rights to guarantee social protection and provision by the state and society when an individual cannot create adequate living conditions for himself and his family.

Agreeing with Putilo's opinion, it can be said that since women are the most vulnerable part of society, it is important for the state to guarantee adequate living conditions for them.

V.A.Ivanenko and V.S.Ivanenko in their study "Social rights are a combination of rights and freedoms recognized by society and the state and defined in normative legal norms to ensure and protect certain abilities, interests and opportunities of each person for social development. they write [2].

According to Yu.I.Leybo, social rights are essentially the rights to ensure legal guarantees and the opportunity to fully claim legal privileges[3].

Yu.I. Leybo's definition, it is possible to ensure gender equality by providing legal privileges to women. It is necessary for the state to create suitable conditions and privileges for women to work and strengthen their health, taking into account their role in the family and their physical capabilities, along with gaining a profession, working, getting paid for it, and actively participating in social and political life [5].

Based on the above-mentioned scientific views, we can define the concept of "women's social rights" as follows:

"Women's social rights are a system of legal norms that regulate relations aimed at ensuring a decent standard of living and social protection, guaranteed in accordance with the constitutional status of women." [6]

This definition was based on the following:

first, the characteristics of women's social rights are determined by their constitutional status;

secondly, taking into account the role of motherhood in guaranteeing social rights, determining benefits and ensuring social protection;

thirdly, rights that ensure a decent lifestyle for women (the right to employment, equal pay for equal work, health care, social security, housing) [7].

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The relevance of studying the political system of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Salomov Jasur Botirovich

Phd Student, Academy of Science of Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan, as one of the most developed states of Central Asia, was able to create such a model of the political system that most effectively and painlessly brought the country out of the political and socio-economic crisis caused by the collapse of the Soviet Union.

Uzbekistan has refused various kinds of experiments in relation to the activities of political institutions and the formation of a peculiar political elite.

For example, in Kyrgyzstan they are still unsuccessfully trying to establish a European-style parliamentary republic that would conduct consolidated activities with the president.

Unfortunately, this path significantly complicated the mechanism for the adoption of legal documents by the parliament, led to increased lobbying and inconsistency in the ranks of factions of political parties in Kyrgyzstan.

Such a system of party membership has been formed, which, in fact, reflects clan or regional confrontations, as a result of which the political system is inflamed into different groups.

The system of state power of this republic, which theoretically refers to a rationalized model of parliamentarism, is sometimes even called a “new mutant form of democracy”¹.

Accordingly, there were no guarantees that a similar trend would not be present in Uzbek society. Therefore, for the first time, a more restrained, perhaps even classic version of a presidential republic with elements of authoritarianism was chosen.

¹ Shamsov T. Politicheskiye rejimi i ix osobennosti v usloviyax Sentralnoaziatskogo regiona (sravnitelniy analiz) Avtoreferat dissertatsii na soisk. uch.step. kand.polit.nauk. Kurgan-Tyubinskiy gosudarstvenniy universitet. – Dushanbe, 2015. P.9

Many experts have come to the conclusion that almost all the states of the region, and Uzbekistan, respectively, have built “super-presidential” regimes, that is, political systems with an emphasis on overly personified power².

One can only partly agree with this conclusion. Indeed, in some countries of Central Asia there is a practice of “personalizing” the heads of state (for example, in Kazakhstan - “Elbasy”, in Tajikistan - “Peshvoi Millat”, in Turkmenistan the previous president has the form of address - “Turkmenbashi”, the current one – “Arkadag”), as well as the maximum empowerment of the management of domestic and foreign policy with a dubious prospect of further decentralization (Turkmenistan, Tajikistan).

In Uzbekistan, however, such initiatives have always been opposed, considering them extremely inappropriate.

Regarding the processes associated with the decentralization of power in the republic, it is worth noting that, in fact, for a certain time, the government of the country was concentrated in the hands of only a few institutions of power. The gradual transfer of powers "from top to bottom" began in the 2000s, when the transition to a bicameral parliament was carried out, the legal infrastructure of local self-government bodies was strengthened, and the powers of the Cabinet of Ministers and regional administrations were expanded. That is, the president was now authorized to ensure only the coordinated functioning and interaction of state authorities³.

The concentration of power in the hands of the president in the early stages of state building, in our opinion, is the most necessary condition for preventing political tension in power structures. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, this helped to strengthen the mechanism for the implementation of laws and other state decisions, to accelerate perestroika processes in the political, interethnic and other spheres. In this regard, the Uzbek practice of state building proves the veracity of our judgments.

² Halbach U. Das Regime der Präsidenten. Entwicklung und Zusammenarbeit. 1999. 40.Jg.Heft 2. S. 39–41.

³ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2014 Art.89. [Electronic resource] //URL: <http://constitution.uz/ru> Date of access: 16.02.2021

In developing this statement, we also note that this political phenomenon manifests a natural tendency of social development in the transition period. Liberation from totalitarianism requires huge efforts, phased in, including at the initial stage - a strong authoritarian power capable of evolving towards real democracy⁴. According to E. Yusupova's correct remark, "the democratization of society in Uzbekistan, the instillation and institutionalization of democratic forms of political self-organization of society cannot be reached by mechanical transplantation of ready-made forms, principles and institutions of Western democracy. As experience over the years of independence shows, democratization in Uzbekistan requires a phased implementation of the principles of democracy. This is connected simultaneously with the process of formation of a new political consciousness, adequate to the processes of democratization of society⁵."

We consider it appropriate to emphasize that today Uzbekistan is the only country in the region that carries out political modification of the existing political system. The coming to power of a new team after the early presidential elections in 2016 led to a variety of political processes that led to certain changes in the political regime, the activities of political actors and institutions.

Modification processes have affected all branches of government: the role of parliament in the implementation of socio-political reforms has increased dramatically, political parties have actively begun to promote their interests in the country's legislation, the judicial branch is undergoing a serious restructuring stage, the powers of khokims of regions and districts have been noticeably expanded and systematized, the process of media activation is underway by ensuring all their rights and freedoms, which led to the maximum openness of their activities.

However, with a certain degree of confidence, we can note that, despite the liberalization, the most important core of the state administration system and the political system remains the presidential form of government.

⁴ Stratifikatsionnie protsessi obshestva Uzbekistana v kontekste istoricheskix protsessov / Otvet. red. M.A. Raximov, N.R. Maxkamova. – Tashkent, 2014. P. 165

⁵ Yusupova E. Natsionalniy mentalitet i politicheskoye soznaniye v protsesse razvitiya demokraticeskogo obshestva v Uzbekistane. Demokratizatsiya i prava cheloveka. 2017. №4. P.94

This process will also require separate scientific attention and will become a kind of starting point in a comparative study of both the former political system of Uzbekistan (until 2016) and the political systems of neighboring states.

Summarizing the above-mentioned, we note that the relevance of studying the processes of democratic transformation of the political system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is due to a number of reasons:

firstly, today in Uzbekistan and beyond its borders the issues of functioning of some elements and subjects of the political system of the republic are widely considered, however, there is a need for comprehensive work devoted to the study of the entire structure using an interdisciplinary approach

secondly, an institutional study of the political system of the Republic of Uzbekistan will make it possible to draw a conclusion about the effectiveness of its activities in the political, social and economic life of the country;

thirdly, both for the domestic researcher and for the entire world scientific community, a comparative analysis of the activities and organizational and legal structure of the political system of the Republic of Uzbekistan with states similar and dissimilar in their political regime and type is of great interest;

fourthly, after the extraordinary presidential elections of 2016, international research centers focused their attention on the large-scale reforms initiated by the new leadership, a number of significant works were published, where the problems and prospects of the socio-political, financial and economic life of the Uzbek society in the new conditions were identified. Accordingly, these works are also of interest to researchers, through which it will be possible to compare approaches to estimating the two periods⁶.

⁶ Mjuša Sever Judicial and Governance Reform in Uzbekistan. Central Asia-Caucasus Institute and Silk Road Studies Program, Silk Road Paper, March, 2018; Mamuka Tsereteli the Economic Modernization of Uzbekistan. Central Asia-Caucasus Institute and Silk Road Studies Program, April, 2018; Anthony C. Bowyer Political Reform in Mirziyoyev's Uzbekistan: Elections, Political Parties and Civil Society. Central Asia-Caucasus Institute and Silk Road Studies Program, 2018.; Uzbekistan: A New Model for Reform in the Muslim World by S. Frederick Starr and Svante E. Cornell Central Asia-Caucasus Analyst May 12, 2018, <http://silkroadstudies.org/publications/joint-center-publications/item/13295-uzbekistan-a-new-model-for-reform-in-the-muslim-world.html>; Petra Stykov, "Uzbekistan – Mirziyoyev's First

CONTENTS**ECONOMY**

Hakimov Nodir Nazarovich - Theoretical and methodological basis of the organization of state financial control. 3

HISTORY

Bakhtiyor Sabirjonovich Boltabaev - At the end of the 19th century and at the beginning of the 20th century, the administrative-territorial division of Turkestan and the adoption of management regulations. 7

MEDICINE

Sadykov R.A., Khodzhiev D.Sh., Sultanov S.A., Kadyrov M.Zh., Sharifjonov S.M. - Application of the hemoben hemostatic implant in the model of spleen damage in the background of hypo coagulation. 12

Abdirimova G.I., Nazirova S.H., Safarova Sh.U. - Dependence of the state of teeth and oral hygiene in children with a changeable bite. 15

PEDAGOGY

Ishkobilova Khulkar - Negative and positive concepts within the lexeme "family". 17

Sh R. Akramov - The role of independent study in foreign language teaching. 20

Umurzokov Zokir - Informatics as an essential component of lyceum education. 23

STATE AND LAW

Dildora Anvarovna Anvarova - Legal nature of women's social rights. 27

Salomov Jasur Botirovich - The relevance of studying the political system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 30